

ANALYSIS OF THE APPLICATION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TECHNOLOGY IN CORPORATE MANAGEMENT*Sadigova S.,**UNEC Master(MBA)**ORCID 0000-0003-2456-3871**Guliyeva A.**Ataturk University**ORCID 000-0002-7678-4521***ABSTRACT**

The purpose of this article is to determine the prospects for using artificial intelligence (AI) technologies to improve the efficiency of corporate governance in general and to assess the prospects for its application to solve operational and strategic management problems. Currently, two paradigms have been formed that study the prospects for using AI in organizational research: a paradigm that considers artificial intelligence as a set of meta-algorithms capable of finding algorithms for solving specific corporate governance problems, and a paradigm that considers artificial intelligence as a means of optimizing human behavior in an organization. The process of making management decisions at the board level is highlighted as a key area of application of artificial intelligence in corporate governance. The capabilities of AI to improve the efficiency of making management decisions are identified and defined. Among them, the following can be distinguished: ensuring the necessary volume and variety of information with less resource consumption, rapid analysis of large data sets, development of reliable scenarios of the consequences of decisions made, impartiality of decisions, and others. Artificial intelligence technologies are already a useful tool for improving the efficiency of making management decisions, as shown by a number of examples from the practice of Russian corporations. The difficulties and problems that stand in the way of the widespread use of artificial intelligence technologies are analyzed: insufficient development of legislation regulating their use, protection of intellectual property in this area, data confidentiality; lack of clarity regarding responsibility for making risky decisions based on the use of artificial intelligence and their consequences. The use of artificial intelligence in corporate management is limited by a number of ethical problems associated with responsibility for the consequences of decisions made, a low level of legal support for its use and specific risks, the methodology for working with which requires further development.

Keywords: Corporate governance, business processes, artificial intelligence, management decision-making process, board of directors, competitive advantage.

Introduction

In its modern meaning, the concept of artificial intelligence (AI) emerged in the mid-20th century. Its content changed as technical capabilities for machine copying of individual functions of human intelligence developed (starting with such simple ones as counting) to the current state, when artificial intelligence is a powerful technological complex that can not only replace humans in solving numerous computational problems, but also simulate individual functions of human consciousness. A.Y. Petrunin notes, in the process of developing ideas about AI, "truly promising tools of artificial intelligence were proposed: models of neural networks, genetic and, more broadly, evolutionary algorithms, fuzzy logic, multi-agent systems, reflexive control, etc." [Petrunin 2018, 103].

The AI technologies that emerged in the middle of the last century solved only a range of problems limited to mathematical calculations. However, as computer technologies improved, AI received a new impetus for its development. The development of artificial intelligence was especially influenced by the methodology of neural networks, which imitates and copies the organization of the neurons of the nervous systems of living organisms. The peculiarity of a neural network is that it is capable of learning from various tasks and, thanks to this, can determine patterns and identify interdependencies and connections (correlations) between the analyzed data, which cannot be identified in other ways.

This development of AI has ultimately led to the possibility of a broad interpretation of the possibilities of using artificial intelligence in a variety of areas of social practice. Of course, the problems of corporate governance and the assessment of the prospects for solving them using AI have not been left aside.

A certain difficulty in understanding the prospects for using AI in corporate management is the polysemy of the term. Even if we leave aside the common idea that AI is a replacement for human consciousness, potentially leading to a "robot revolt," we can identify two paradigms present in the scientific literature.

The first paradigm is based on the understanding of AI as a set of "meta-algorithms capable of finding algorithms for solving any specific problem" [Ibid., 100], copying the rational process of human thinking.

The second paradigm views AI as a means of optimizing human behavior in an organization, especially in those aspects that are related to making and implementing important (primarily strategic) decisions. In particular, American researchers S. Russell and P. Norvig consider the totality of behavioral manifestations of human thinking as "externalization of thinking," which implies a high level of correlation between mental acts and organizational behavior of people [Russel, Norvig 2021, 17]. Within the framework of this paradigm, AI is understood as a kind of logical machine that describes and prescribes the behavior of people in an organization as rationally acting subjects.

This behavioral understanding assumes that AI can only be used if people in organizations act based solely on rational considerations.

1 By “corporate governance” we mean the governance of large public companies with share capital and separated functions of strategic (board of directors) and operational (CEO, administration) governance [Monks, Minow 2011].

However, not all problems can be described rationally. Emotions, desires, the desire for personal gain, numerous (often hidden) risks, etc. are often “mixed” with rational reasoning. That is, the problems are made “soft”: their boundaries are blurred, uncertain, and the methods of solution are not obvious. This is how most of the most important organizational problems look like - from developing a strategy to assigning compensation to the top management personnel of the company. But this does not make the situation with the use of AI hopeless: the AI task in the case of such “soft” problems can be solved by building meta-algorithms using large databases that take into account all (or almost all) the diversity of human behavioral reactions in the course of the company's daily work.

Despite the existence of various understandings of the nature and significance of AI for organizational research, the rapid development of the discipline and the new opportunities it provides could not but have a significant impact on the theory and practice of management in the 21st century. Various aspects of such influence are widely discussed in modern scientific literature on management and business theory. Thus, in particular, T. Taulli considers the prospects for the use of machine learning in organizational management, neural network algorithms for planning and control, and the use of AI in the robotization of production processes [Taulli 2021]. A. Postolit raises questions about the possibility of software implementation of neural network elements and the construction of multilayer neural networks that ensure the coordination of complex projects [Postolit 2021], while M. Broussard warns against excessive optimism expressed by a number of authors who express confidence that, in principle, there are no restrictions on the use of AI in organizational management [Broussard 2021]. More specific issues of using AI in corporate management are also considered. For example, N. Sonie et al. propose ways to use AI to promote innovative products to the market [Sonietal. 2020], and I. Enholm et al. analyze the prospects for using AI in value-based management (MBV) [Enholm et al. 2021].

On the other hand, since the beginning of the 21st century, major transnational corporations such as Apple, Facebook2, Amazon, Google, Microsoft and a number of others have shown great interest in the possibilities of using AI to solve numerous business problems. They invest huge amounts of money in AI research and are already using various developments in this area in their practical activities. The modern trend towards reducing the cost of AI platforms and increas-

ing their availability has allowed not only large corporations to work with them, but also specialized companies and even startups [Gusev, Dobridnyuk 2017].

The problems and prospects of using AI technologies in various fields are actively discussed by the international scientific community and cover a wide range of topics. However, there are few studies focusing on the use of AI technologies in the field of business and corporate management. The topic of introducing AI technologies in the field of corporate management is only developing and remains poorly developed in the scientific literature. Taking this circumstance into account, the purpose of our study is to determine the prospects for using AI technologies to improve the efficiency of corporate management in general and to assess the prospects for its application to solve operational and strategic management problems.

If we stay within the framework of the first of the paradigms we have outlined above, AI is understood not only as technologies that imitate human thinking, but also as technologies capable of self-learning, which means the ability of an artificial intelligent system to create meta-algorithms that allow solving new problems that the system has not encountered before. In organizational management, such tasks are most typical for the process of making complex decisions, and by “complex” decisions we mean decisions that have a significant impact on the company’s development prospects, the ability to achieve the established mission, and often simply its continued existence. These may be, for example, decisions regarding the choice of development strategy, large-scale reorganizations, changes, the choice of certain anti-crisis measures.

There are various sources of options for solving problems of this kind. In some cases, a good basis is the personal experience of the manager, his ability to organize the process of participatory decision-making, the use of the “collective mind” of subordinates, communications with colleagues who have encountered similar problems and whose experience can be adapted to solve one's own problems. A special case in terms of the impossibility of rational reconstruction of the decision-making process is the situation of “insight”, “a voice from above” or awareness of the correct decision, as was the case with the phenomenon of the image of the periodic table of elements to D. Mendeleev during sleep. In general, such decision-making processes can be characterized as methodological chaos, which is subsequently often interpreted as a rational process, where the stages and interrelation of the sequence of actions leading to success are clearly distinguished. Many examples of this kind of rational reconstruction of decision-making situations can be found in the memoirs and biographies of famous business leaders - from G. Ford [Ford 2017] and L. Iacocca [Iacocca 2022] to the founder of Apple Corporation S. Jobs [Prashkevich, Soloviev 2019].

The rational process for making important corporate decisions is well understood and verified. It is typically presented in eight stages (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Stages of the rational process of making management decisions

Since the early 1970s, corporate management (primarily in industry) has widely used the capabilities of computers to collect information and evaluate alternatives for solving production problems. An increasing number of decision-making procedures were formalized, and an increasing number of decision options were analyzed by computers it seemed that in the foreseeable future all stages of the decision-making process would be formalized, and the process itself optimized. G. Simon and J. March noted in their works of this period that there are no fundamental obstacles to the algorithmization of all stages of decision-making - the problem lies only in the speed of existing computers, which is visibly losing its relevance against the backdrop of rapid progress in computer technology [March, Simon 1998].

They were right in many ways. Indeed, almost all stages of rational decision-making are successfully computerized, but the problem remains with the development of criteria for evaluating alternatives (stage 4) and an even more acute problem with assessing the need to revise the criteria and put forward its options. It is in this area that people are guided not only by rational considerations, but also by hidden incentives: for example, a manager may insist on revising the criteria for evaluating alternatives in order to ensure support for a solution that is beneficial to him, providing additional personal income, implementing the practice of nepotism in personnel decisions, or executing an order of a government agency that clearly runs counter to the goals of the organization. R. Smith captures this idea as follows: "AI has shown that models of human thinking based on idealizations of mathematics or logic do not embody real, reliable decision-making in the face of ontological uncertainty observed in humans. Thus, caution should be exercised when attempting to model the decision-making process of economic agents using similar tools" [Smith2016, 34-35].

This "ontological uncertainty" gives rise to the phenomenon of "humanization" of AI, which means including in the sphere of AI the consideration of human motives for decision-making and the possibility of preventing the reproduction of human errors⁴.

The task is to find ways to combine AI with the unique capabilities of humans for decision-making. A number of researchers note the prospects of this path and even the synergistic effects that arise from such interaction.

Thus, the American researcher M. Jarrahi develops the idea of the complementarity of people and artificial intelligence, exploring how each of these parties can contribute to the processes of making organizational decisions, which are usually characterized by uncertainty, complexity, and ambiguity. He notes that, "with greater computing power for processing information and an analytical approach, AI can expand human capabilities in solving complex issues, while people can still offer a more holistic, intuitive approach to working with uncertainty and ambiguity" [Jarrahi 2018, 577].

AI technologies can provide the necessary volume and wide range of information needed to make strategic decisions, which reduces the need for qualified personnel to ensure this important function of the corporation. In this regard, as noted by F. Provost and T. Fawcett, fewer human and time resources will be required, and small teams for developing decisions will increase the efficiency and speed of their adoption due to the new capabilities provided by AI [Provost, Fawcett 2021, 55].

A person has a limit to the speed and volume of assimilation and processing of information, and exceeding it leads to psychological and physiological problems, which in the case of a manager affects the quality of decisions made and management in general. The solution is here are often found in simplifying the situation by constructing a hierarchy of essential and non-essential data, when the latter are ignored. This way of overcoming information overload creates the risk of error, when fragmented data essential for the decision falls into the category of non-essential, as a result of which they are "quite reasonably" not taken into account, but the consequences of such an error can be very sad. To avoid it, one can consider the prospects of using AI, for which practically any data arrays are not a problem [Fiori 2011, 587].

The use of AI technologies to analyze large amounts of data allows us to respond to the rapid growth of data and the high dynamism of environmental parameters in modern realities. Assessing their prospects, American researcher M. Hilb argues that “by analyzing a large array of diverse data, AI technologies can generate more reliable scenarios for the consequences of decisions made, thereby improving forecasting capabilities” [Hilb 2020, 861].

The researchers tried to find out how top corporate managers assess the prospects for using AI for decision-making. To this end, V. Kolbjørnsrud, R. Amico and R. Thomas surveyed 1,770 corporate managers from 14 countries, including directors responsible for digital transformation in their companies. It was also found that corporate managers at all levels spend more than half of their working time coordinating work and monitoring, that is, completely routine procedures. At the same time, they expect that these functions can be gradually transferred to artificial intelligence with the introduction of AI technologies, and they would prefer to use the freed up time to solve more “non-standard” problems, using their creative potential and the creative potential of others [Kolbjørnsrud et al. 2016].

Another study by A. Trunk, H. Birkel, and E. Hartmann examined the prospects for integrating AI into strategic decision-making under uncertainty in the strategic management literature. They found that many authors are very cautious about this prospect, as they are convinced that making such decisions requires abilities that only humans possess. In this case, they consider AI technologies only as support for the decision-making process (primarily in terms of processing large amounts of data). However, many authors were found to believe that AI technologies and people will complement each other in developing corporate strategies [Trunk et al. 2020].

This point of view is developed, in particular, by the Australian researcher M. Hilb, who identifies five areas of application of AI technologies in corporate governance and in the decision-making activities of the Board of Directors (BoD) [Hilb 2020]. Firstly, AI can be used as an auxiliary tool, a kind of set of tools for choosing the best alternative solution, a means of evaluating a significantly larger number of solution options based on an incomparably larger number of parameters than is available even to the most sophisticated human intelligence. In addition, the use of AI allows for additional automation of consolidation and reporting processes in the company, providing members of the BoD with data in real time, which increases the transparency of the decision-making process.

Second, AI can be seen as an extension of the human intellect, just as it extends the range of actions of the human hand that holds a sword or a violin bow. As such tools that extend the capabilities of the mind,

AI-based predictive models can be considered, which help to develop increasingly reliable scenarios and models, and introduce a contingency methodology into the decision-making process, allowing one to predict even the most distant consequences of decision-making.

Thirdly, with increasing weight and influence, AI can be applied in a situation where some functions (especially those requiring large amounts of computation) in decision-making are transferred to artificial intelligence, and people use the results obtained in this way as a basis for final decision-making.

Fourthly, moving along the logic of the increasing importance of AI, it acquires the functions of autonomous intelligence, expressing its opinion on certain problems requiring solutions. In essence, AI becomes an independent member of the SD, as described in the above example.

Finally, AI becomes the “brain” of the corporation, performing the most important functions of the SD (from strategy development, appointments to senior administrative positions in the company). This option assumes fully automated business management, planning the future of the corporation and developing measures to achieve it. Of course, at present this looks like a flight of fancy, where there are no restrictions, but at the same time, no rational restrictions have been found that, in principle, prohibit this kind of development of the strategic management process of the company.

Use of AI technologies in Russian corporations: opportunities and problems

Russia has traditionally been one of the leading powers in the field of information technology development in general and AI in particular. Therefore, the documents adopted by government agencies in the last decade that define the development of AI technologies should be assessed as realistic. First of all, this applies to the “National Strategy for the Development of Artificial Intelligence for the Period up to 2030” adopted in 2019, which is a comprehensive plan that ensures “a high degree of influence of technological solutions developed on the basis of artificial intelligence on the performance of an organization and a person, including those related to making management decisions”⁵. As noted in the strategy, it serves, among other things, as a basis for the development of planned and program-targeted products of joint-stock companies with state participation in terms of AI development, and its implementation is ensured by the coordinated actions of many participants, including joint-stock companies with state participation.

In terms of specifying the “National Strategy”, in 2019 the Ministry of Communications of the Russian Federation developed a “Roadmap for the Development of End-to-End Digital Technology “Neurotechnology and Artificial Intelligence”, which describes the main areas of AI application: freeing people from monotonous work through automatic software creation; support in decision-making; automation of hazardous types of work; support for communications between people. As stated in the “Roadmap”, artificial intelligence acts as a “new electricity” designed to improve the quality of life and improve the well-being of society.

As a result of the implementation of the AI system, the productivity of employees working with documents increased by 1.5 times, and due to improved payment discipline of counterparties, it was possible to save from 3 to 4 percent of the contract amount [Ibid.]⁹.

Successfully implemented AI technology at Sberbank PJSC to monitor information about counterparties on the Internet and search for potential clients for the banking business.

Before the introduction of AI, daily media monitoring and analysis of news aggregator data was done manually. Many employees searched for information on the Internet and other open sources that could be used to draw conclusions about the sustainability of companies. However, about 84% of important information was missed.

In order to improve the efficiency of this business process, an AI-driven Russian and foreign media monitoring system was implemented. It independently, without human intervention, searches for information about companies and their environment, creates a structured dossier, analyzes industry news and its impact on business, monitors key events (bankruptcy, license revocation, etc.). And the news that has already been selected and ranked by importance is analyzed by experts and the bank's administration. In addition, the system finds and evaluates people interested in the services provided by the bank, identifies their needs and evaluates them as potential clients (leads).

There is also ample evidence that the use of AI by Russian companies improves the productivity of management work in decision-making at the board level, for auditing, checking financial statements, automating document flow, assessing the dynamics of economic and financial indicators, detecting fraud, recruiting personnel for responsible positions, organizing compensation payments to the corporation's top management, determining trends in changes in shareholder capital and improving many other areas of corporate governance.

Despite the successful experience of using AI technologies in corporate management, there are certain difficulties along the way. First of all, we note the lack of development of legislation regulating its use. In particular, we are talking about the problems of legal regulation of data related to confidentiality, intellectual property, security and liability, ethics. The task of developing new legislation is becoming urgent, especially since, as noted by Russian and foreign researchers, the rapid spread of AI is already ahead of the development and implementation of the regulatory framework and mechanisms designed to manage it [Vorobyeva, Salakhutdinov 2020; Goralski, Tan 2020]

Like any other technology, AI technologies carry risks. These are risks associated with the safety of using AI (both in the physical and financial, reputational sense), with the delegation of responsibility for decisions taken, risks associated with the reorganization of the accountability system in the company, risks of loss of confidentiality of software and its deliberate damage, and a number of others.

The safety of using AI technologies means protection from negative consequences that may arise during their implementation. In order to ensure safety, artificial intelligence technologies must undergo a verification procedure and be adjusted accordingly, as well as build in protective mechanisms that prevent negative interference.

Accountability is directly related to the AI decision-making process and implies its transparency and verifiability. The decision-making process should be built with criteria that help to achieve decision transparency, i.e., the decision-making process is reproducible and explainable through logical reasoning.

Liability is one of the most pressing issues raised by AI technologies. Who is responsible if AI technologies cause damage? If the damage is due to design or manufacturing defects, the manufacturer is responsible. But if the wrong decisions are not directly related to design and manufacturing, there is no clear culprit and it is unclear how disciplinary measures can be applied in this case.

Ethics and ethical issues become increasingly important as AI technologies advance. Artificial intelligence cannot understand abstract concepts such as fairness, responsibility, loyalty to the organization and its individual leaders; thus, ethical principles and judgments cannot influence the choices made by AI. But it is easy to imagine a situation in which AI makes optimal decisions within the framework of the logic used, but which, due to their negative ethical load, a reputation-conscious leader would never make.

The next risk area is software availability. This poses a dilemma: should the source code of AI programs be closed or open? Each of these options has its pros and cons. On the one hand, open source can speed up the development of AI through the use of crowdsourcing, when anyone can try to change the AI program and "sell" the result to an interested party. However, openness increases the threat of unauthorized use of AI technologies. On the other hand, closed access to software minimizes the threat of abuse when using technologies, but, as noted in the publication Alliance global corporate & specialty, slows down the development of AI technologies.

In summary, the use of AI technologies opens up many opportunities and at the same time carries serious risks. Therefore, when implementing projects based on the use of AI, it is necessary to apply a balanced approach that takes into account not only the benefits of implementing and using AI, but also the problems that inevitably arise.

Conclusion

Today, AI technologies are of particular interest and are, as noted, the most promising. They carry both new opportunities and new threats that must be taken into account when implementing and applying them. AI technologies are developing and finding their application in a variety of areas, including corporate governance. And one of the areas of application of AI technologies in corporate governance is the process of making management decisions.

In connection with the stated goal of describing and assessing the prospects for the introduction and application of AI technologies in corporate management practice, identifying their positive effects, the main emphasis was placed on determining the capabilities of AI to improve the efficiency of management decision-making and, above all, strategic decisions made by the company's board of directors. The most important of these effects are a multiple increase in the volume of

information used to develop decision alternatives and a significant reduction in resource costs; rapid analysis of large data sets; development of reliable scenarios for the consequences of decisions taken; an increase in the quality of decisions (their impartiality, a sharp decrease in the possibility of reflecting opportunistic sentiments in them that conflict with corporate goals and values), and a number of others.

Understanding the potential for achieving such positive effects, as well as the limitations of using AI, makes the use of these technologies more productive and meaningful.¹

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